

CLINICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE PROGNOSIS OF DENTAL DISEASES IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR PATHOLOGY

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Annotation. Currently, pathological prognosis is very important in all areas of health care. However, although this prediction is of great importance and scientific and practical importance in dentistry, we have not yet received information about the prophylactic model of the individual risk of periodontitis in patients with cardiovascular disease. In these cases, it is important to individually assess and predict the risk of periodontitis in patients with arrhythmias. These studies serve as the basis for identifying patients at high risk of periodontitis, grouping them for dental monitoring, and taking measures to eliminate the negative consequences of periodontitis in cardiovascular disease. The need to solve this problem is the basis of this research.

Keywords: periodontitis, cardiovascular system (CVS), arrhythmia, homeostasis, oral cavity, somatic diseases.

Purpose of the study: to develop a model to individually predict the risk of dental diseases in patients with cardiovascular disease and evaluate its effectiveness.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted at the clinic of Samarkand State Medical University . A retrospective Environmental Control study was conducted. We examined patients with cardiac pathologies between 112 and 36 years of age (average age 45.32-0.22 years) who were hospitalized in the treatment dentistry department. The diagnosis of arrhythmia and periodontitis is based on WHO standards and recommendations, revised according to the

International Classification of diseases 10. Inclusion criteria are patients who have previously been diagnosed with arrhythmia . After diagnosis, all patients underwent a comprehensive dental examination. Take fluid and blood samples by mouth. After completing the dental examination of each patient, the dentist fill out the patient's medical record (form 043/Y) and transfer the data from the hospital patient's medical record (form 003/y). Taking into account the purpose of the study, patients with arrhythmias were divided into two groups: the main group with periodontitis (patients) and the control group without periodontitis (patients). According to the principles of evidence-based medicine, people of the same sex and age are selected in the formation of the main and control groups. All patients signed a consent form to participate in the study . The research plan is reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee. When determining risk factors, we considered the multifactorial nature of heart disease and periodontitis and their dependence on the complex of medical and Social Risk Factors and metabolic disorders of the most important homeostatic systems of the body. In this context, the nature and changes of Medical Risk Factors and lipid profiles were studied. During the study period, the indicators that most affected the two pathological processes studied were determined. Use the periodontal inflammation and destruction index and oral hygiene indicators (PMA, Pi, Mühlemann, OHI-s) to assess the severity of periodontal injury. The Kullback reference index is used to assess the symptomatic significance of periodontitis risk factors in patients with arterial hypertension and to determine the G(K) value. Since the presence or absence of relevant variable periodontitis can only be characterized by two values of 0 to 1 (presence/absence of periodontitis), the possibility of periodontitis is evaluated in patients with arrhythmia. A predictive model created using the binary logical regression method. Use MS Excel 2007, MS Access 2007, Statistica 8.0, and statgraphics Centurion XV (version 16.2.04) to perform statistical processing and analysis of the data obtained.

Result: significant but statistically irrelevant risk factors were selected as dependent variables. The selection of risk factors is to compare with other indicators of the same type through the "discrete correlation Pleiades" method, taking into account the main characteristics (Pleiades), which is necessary for the risk of periodontitis. Therefore, the model does not have many parameters that significantly affect the severity of pathology, but appears due to the existence of the disease and does not begin its development. As a result of the calculations, the following indicators were selected to create a model of the risk of periodontitis in patients with cardiovascular system pathologies:

Periodontitis development probability score scale: 0-0.39-low, 0.40-0.69-medium, 0.70-1.00-high. Combined with the consistency of the scale of the indicators included in the research and the model, their contribution to the risk of periodontitis in patients with arrhythmias can be compared and evaluated. According to the obtained coefficients, all these factors contribute to an increased risk of periodontitis in general in patients with heart disease. Use the measurement coefficient and Fisher's criterion to check the statistical significance of the equation. It turns out that in the studied case, 96.98% of the total variability of Y is explained by changes in the XJ factor. The resulting model is a tool for evaluating the prognosis of the possibility of periodontitis in patients with arrhythmia, taking into account medical characteristics and blood lipid profile parameters. A structured model used to predict the development of periodontitis was clinically evaluated in 112 patients with cardiovascular disease, of whom 85 (75.31% of patients with hypertension) were diagnosed with periodontitis. After a thorough examination, it is predicted that 80 (72.84%) patients with arrhythmias are most likely to suffer from periodontitis. When evaluating the likelihood of periodontitis in patients with cardiovascular disease, the sensitivity of the model was 96.72%. Of the 30 patients who did not have periodontitis at the time of the examination, 2 (5.00%) had a low to moderate risk of periodontitis. Therefore, the specificity of the periodontal

disease development model is 29.50%. The total diagnostic accuracy rate of this method is 95.57%. The model of research results is very approximate, which allows us to conclude that in the practice of general practitioners and periodontists, it is necessary to predict the development of periodontitis in patients with arrhythmias and use it in groups to provide targeted interdisciplinary interactions and significantly reduce inflammation and the development mechanisms of destructive periodontal heart disease.

Conclusion. Based on the developed symptomatic model, the characteristics of somatic cell pathology and the individual medical characteristics of patients with periodontitis in general are determined. The main risk factors were identified, including age, history of genetic disease, poor smoking habits, arrhythmic disease stage, presence and number of chronic diseases, total cholesterol in the blood, triglyceride levels and atherosclerosis index. Based on equations developed taking into account the smallest group of Main medical and laboratory parameters, the probability of periodontitis in patients with cardiovascular disease can be estimated. After clinical examination, the computer program "forecast modeling of the possibility of periodontitis in patients with somatic diseases" can be recommended for actual medical care.

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